

Communicating Astrobiology: Words versus Numbers, Cause versus Consequence, Fact versus Fiction

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Recently, NASA scientists and administrators have proposed a numerical scale for quantifying the Confidence of Life Detection – the CoLD scale [1]. Although the stated goal is to minimize damaging public trust with premature or overly-confident claims of detecting life beyond Earth, the CoLD scale is an inapt and easily abused tool that will do little to address the misleading terminology and sensational narratives that plague both public and scientific communications from the astrobiology community. By failing to acknowledge, much less address, the root cause(s) of these communication problems, the CoLD scale can only address the symptoms while allowing the underlying disease to progress. That the arrival of misleading claims could be confidently anticipated by the developers of the CoLD scale is itself a measure of the strength of the disease. The root cause(s) run deep and cannot be cured with a numerical scale.

The inaugural issue of *Nature Astronomy* warned of harm to public trust if the science community continued to use imprecise and misleading wording such as ‘Super-Earth’ or ‘Earth2.0’ [2,3,4]. The trend has, however, continued and the public now also hears about ‘Super-Habitable Planets’ and ‘Goldilocks Stars.’ The catchy wording grabs attention by design. At the same time, it sends misinformation in ways that numbers cannot correct [5].

Misleading terms go hand-in-hand with overly-confident narratives. The public has been told by NASA administrators and scientists that we will have “strong indications of life beyond Earth within a decade and definitive evidence in 20-30 years” [6], “that finding a second Earth is not a matter of if but when” [7], and that “super-Earths are super-habitable” [8]. Those statements demonstrate how the community often presents untested hypotheses as firm conclusions. This abuses public trust and is in stark contrast with the history of the first exoplanet discoveries in which at least two groups withdrew or withheld claims out of abundant caution [9].

Introducing a numerical scale without addressing the terms and narratives used to communicate scientific results will not diminish the transfer of misinformation. The CoLD scale, by quantifying the professional judgements of scientists (which scientists?), can formalize miscommunication. Attaching a mandated number to a science communication provides cover for the continued use of misleading words and overly-confident narratives. Headlines like ‘Super-Earth, with CoLD rating 1, found in Habitable-Zone of Goldilocks Star’ will confuse more than they clarify. Announcements such as ‘Life Detection of the 3rd Scale Has Been Made’, which amounts to marketing versus scientific measurement, will only prime the public for the anticipated next level of detection, whether or not key measurements are attainable. The Spielbergesque assonance will also send mixed messages.

Subjecting the public to the rise and fall of a scale, deemed important enough to be stamped onto all communications, can decrease public trust. The introduction of the Terror Alert Scale by the Department of Homeland Security in the wake of the 9/11 attacks illustrates how a scale introduced to the public diminished rather than increased confidence in a federal agency charged with an important task. In a 2009 review of the scale shortly before

its abandonment [10], the Homeland Security Advisory Council concluded that “...at its best, there is currently indifference to the Homeland Security Advisory System and, at worst, there is a disturbing lack of public confidence in the system.” That outcome was the result not only of a vague and poorly constructed scale, but also of its cynical manipulation by those assigning values to the scale [11], circumstances that are by no means unique to the Department of Homeland Security.

To cure the disease, rather than quantify its symptoms, behavioral patterns in the community need to be addressed. The core principles of the field need to be examined to determine what is driving the trend toward catchy versus precise wording, optimistic promises, and overly confident claims. The incentive structures fueling these patterns must be analyzed, and, where necessary, changed [12]. A particular incentive is that catchy words and confident claims draw attention and the career value of attention has increased [13]. This leads to language designed to be evocative and engaging rather than instructive [14].

Astrobiology narratives have begun to converge on the idea that the discovery of life beyond Earth is the most important of discoveries that can be made —a Holy Grail with implications that will shake all of humanity. That idea has emerged as a foundational principle of the field. The goal has shifted from exploration, where we accept what we do or do not find, to finding life. A particular answer has become the goal. Adding a scale designed to assess confidence in that answer simply fuels the foundational shift. The shift brings with it an unhealthy sense of urgency to astrobiology as a discipline. That, in turn, allows sloppy language, efforts to garner public support, and reifications to enter into the field [15]. It can justify the view that humanity deserves all results immediately – without waiting for assessment, verification or validation. Messaging will be positive, wording will lean toward drawing attention, and efforts will be made to maintain public anticipation. A progressive numerical index working up to the final ‘breakthrough’ reinforces that tendency.

We can't predict if astrobiologists, administrators, and journalists will be able to back off from the perceived urgency and existential value of their work, the need to keep it in the spotlight, and the verbal hype and over-promising that comes with that. But we can ask *who is to say what detecting life beyond Earth will mean for humanity?* It may “pass over 99% of humankind without a trace” [16]. There is a touch of hubris in thinking that question can be answered before the fact. Perhaps it's time to get back to exploration at its own cadence, accepting what we find versus setting out to find what we want to accept, and reporting that back to the public free of hype, catchy wording, and overly-confident narratives.

Added in Proof: In an excitement to get results out, astronomers failed to realize that the James Webb Space Telescope (JWST) detectors had not been adequately calibrated [17]. Scientists, who had written papers within two weeks of JWST coming on line, experienced ‘Oh No ’moments and previously released ‘findings ’are being revised in a process described as “thorny and annoying” [17]. Changing ideas based on updated information is a part of science. However, the drive to get results out on time scales faster than required for community assessment is a newer trend that runs counter to the values of science [18]. It exemplifies our thesis for a cause of behavioral trends in astrobiology: The conviction that one's own work is so important that priority must be given to speed and quantity of information over quality control and accuracy of communication to the public and to colleagues. This is a problem that no quantitative scale can address and likely extends well beyond astrobiology.

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Words Matter 01

The English language ... becomes ugly & inaccurate because our thoughts are foolish, but the slovenliness of our language makes it easier for us to have foolish thoughts.

George Orwell

1

Words Matter 02

can I say to
you – words, words
as if all
worlds were there

Robert Creeley

2

Words Matter 03

BS Language: Certain, Evocative, Buzzwords, Taglines, Self-Serving, No Nuance, No Room for Alternatives, Lazy Generalizations.

Selwyn, N. (2016), Minding Our Language, *Learning, Media & Technology* 41: 437-443

... defining characteristic of bullshit: That it attempts to impress rather than to inform;
To be engaging rather than instructive.

Pennycook, G. et al (2015) On the Reception and Detection of Pseudo Profound Bullshit, *Judgment and Decision Making* 10: 549-563.

3

Words Matter 04

Consider two statements from a research paper:

I suggest that ...

vs

It is recognized that ...

The latter will get you attention but can lack full disclosure and full honesty - a radical honesty in the age of attention.

Confidence is good but over-confidence always sinks the ship

4

Sloppy Language Incentives and fuelling the hype machine

I suggest that ... *[YAWN] OH SO BORING*

vs

It is recognized that ... *TED TALK INVITE*

5

Sloppy Language? Put a Number on It

I suggest that ... *[YAWN] OH SO BORING*

vs

It is recognized that ... *TED TALK INVITE*

^
*at level 6 on our
confidence scale*

6

Sloppy Language? Put a Number on It

7

Numbers and Scales

Not a Panacea for Mis-Information

... reliance on numbers and quantitative manipulation minimizes the need for intimate knowledge and personal trust.

Quantification is a way of making decisions without seeming to decide.

8

Numbers and Scales

There is, at best, Indifference and, at worst, a lack of public confidence in the system.

Homeland Security Advisory Council Final Report (2009)

9

Numbers and Scales

There is a Planet that is 0.007 Better than Earth

Building Public Trust ?

← Tweet

@Rainmaker1973

According to an index developed in 2015, Earth is not the most habitable planet found yet. Kepler-442b, a rocky near-Earth-sized exoplanet that is 1206 light-years away from Earth, has a rating of 0.836. On the other hand, Earth has a rating of 0.829 buff.ly/3bJe6QF

7:05 AM · Dec 29, 2022 · 8M Views

7,259 Retweets 1,322 Quote Tweets 61.4K Likes

10

Numbers and Scales

Nigel Tufnel: The numbers all go to eleven. Look, right across the board, eleven, eleven, eleven and...

Marty DiBergi: Oh, I see. And most amps go up to ten?

Nigel Tufnel: Exactly.

Marty DiBergi: Does that mean it's louder? Is it any louder?

Nigel Tufnel: Well, it's one louder, isn't it? It's not ten. You see, most blokes, you know, will be playing at ten. You're on ten here, all the way up, all the way up, all the way up, you're on ten on your guitar. Where can you go from there? Where?

Marty DiBergi: I don't know.

Nigel Tufnel: Nowhere. Exactly. What we do is, if we need that extra push over the cliff, you know what we do?

Marty DiBergi: Put it up to eleven.

Nigel Tufnel: Eleven. Exactly. One louder.

Marty DiBergi: Why don't you just make ten louder and make ten be the top number and make that a little louder?

Nigel Tufnel: [pause] These go to eleven.

Nigel Tufnel

11

These go to eleven.

Nigel Tufnel

12